

A new record of *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew) on *Chilo suppressalis* (Walker) in the Philippines

A. T. Barrion, research assistant, and J. A. Litsinger, associate entomologist, Entomology Department, Cropping Systems Program, International Rice Research Institute

Although natural enemies of *Chilo suppressalis* have been investigated in the Philippines since 1930, no phorid parasites associated with this stem borer species have been reported. We reared *Megaselia scalaris* (Loew) for the first time from striped rice borer larvae and pupae collected in Laguna province, Philippines. The species was previously reported on the yellow rice stem borer *Scirpophaga incertulas* (Walker) in China and Bangladesh.

The parasite was identified by the senior author as *Megaselia scalaris* (L.), which, according to the literature, is cosmopolitan, breeding in cattle wounds or in rotting animals, or plant debris. The adult fly (2.5 mm long) can be distinguished from closely related species by its yellow body and legs, transparent wings, and the lack of a distinct black spot on the apex of each middle femur.

Stem borer larvae parasitized by the fly became immobile, and parasitized pupae turned darker than normal. Just before the host died, 10 to 15 phorid larvae, each about 5 mm long and dirty white in color, emerged from the host and immediately pupated. Laboratory rearing of field - collected borers at IRRI from 10 January to 7 March 1978 showed that the percentage of parasites that emerged from larvae was higher than the percentage that emerged from pupae.

Percentage of parasitization by <i>Megaselia scalaris</i> of striped stem borer <i>C. suppressalis</i> .		
IRRI, 1978.		
Sampling date	Parasitism (%)	
	Larvae	Pupae
10-Jan	5.0 (20)	0 (10)
17-Jan	0 (10)	0 (2)
31-Jan	0 (22)	0 (18)
7-Feb	7.1 (56)	0 (62)
14 Feb	1.8 (56)	1.6 (62)
28-Feb	8.2 (98)	1.0 (104)
7 Mar	2.2 (87)	0 (91)
Numbers in parentheses refer to the number of host borers successfully reared.		

Barrion, A.T. and J.A. Litsinger. 1979. A new record of *Megaselia scalaris* on *Chilo suppressalis* in the Philippines. Int. Rice Res. Newsl. 4(2): 18.